

E-Commerce Website for Company Named Industrial Trading Corporation (A Live Project)

Shruti Shahare, Prof. Rupesh Bobade
NIT Polytechnic, Survey No. 13/2, Katol Road,
Near Fetri, Mahurzari, Nagpur, Maharashtra 441501

Abstract:- There are several purposes of this website one purpose is that this website will be very helpful for users who are seeking fire safety Equipment. As the users need shops, they are not available in the market as easily. This website is providing an Interface to purchase and refill Fire Safety Equipment and Products. Another purpose of having this website is that users can effectively buy the products as there is a rapid growth in the maintenance refilling and installation of fire extinguishers. This website also provides information and videos about the types of extinguishers available in the market and which will suit the user's requirements. This site performs a communication activity between the buyer and seller by making a familiar bonding between them. This website is useful for database management of the company- Industrial Trading Corporation.

Keywords:- Fire Extinguisher, Fire Hydrant, Fire Alarm System, Refilling, E-Commerce, Dynamic.

I. INTRODUCTION

An E-commerce website is like a virtual store where one can buy products online. Where we get to see many varieties of products in one place. Industrial Trading Corporation is a company that sells, refills maintain the Fire Extinguisher, and provides services for the same. An E-commerce website helps in growing the company economically and in every aspect. It helps to reach customers throughout the globe. Making use of an E-commerce website helps to maintain the records of the customers, one can do the payment online, one can manage shipping, and can also provide several other kinds of services.

In this project, we have made use of several different technologies and frameworks. We have divided this website into two parts i.e., Front-end and Back-end. For Front-end we have made use of HTML, CSS, JavaScript, and Bootstrap. Similarly, for the Back-end we have used PHP. We have made use of the Xampp server a local storage to store our data in the database.

II. METHODOLOGY

This section gives us a detailed description of how a user can buy products on the website. The overview working of the website, the various tabs available in the Navigation bar, and how to use them. The E-commerce Website for Industrial Trading Corporation is developed to buy fire products online in the desired quantity at the price available

in the market. So, a user can make use of the following steps to buy the products.

A. ALGORITHM OF PRODUCT PURCHASING ON THE WEBSITE

Step 1: Start

Step 2: Go to the website

Step 3: Select the module/tab

Step 4: If you want to purchase, select the product

Step 5: Click on, call me

Step 6: Enter name, email Id, Contact No, and Message(requirement)

Step 7: Submit

Step 8: If the record is submitted, the record will be shown in a database or the admin login.

Step 9: END

III. LITERATURE REVIEW

The study of some websites already available in the market.

A. SUPREMEX

The Supremex is a proud family-managed business manufacturing, exporting, and distributing fire safety equipment with 30 years of experience.

They provide products and solutions, as the objective of their company.

B. KANEX

Kanex Fire is India's Leading and Trusted fire safety products brand that manufactures several types of fire extinguishers. They provide products, solutions as well as resource centers, and careers.

C. NFPA

NFPA usually publishes an updated version of a standard for the fixed guideway transit and passenger rail systems every 3 years (NFPA 2014).

Rail Fire and Smoke Standards.

D. AMEREX

Amerex Corporation has manufactured quality and innovative firefighting products since 1971. It is leading and providing various contents including environmental safety, corporate responsibility, and multimedia library as a new concept.

E. VALLEY FIRE

Valley Fire Extinguisher Co. Inc. has protected properties and helped to save lives since 1976. They provide services and resources as main.

IV. BLOCK DIAGRAM OF WEBSITE

Image 1: Block Diagram of Website

The above image is the block diagram of the project(website), it consists of various modules such as Home, About Us, Product, Resource Centre, Service, Contact Us, Register, and Admin Login. Some modules such as Product, Resource Centre, and Services have various sub-modules including Search, Types, Booklet, Videos, Refiling, and Maintenance.

V. STRUCTURE & TECHNIQUE

As mentioned in the Block diagram, The website has various modules such as - Home, About Us, Product, Resource Centre, Service, Contact Us, Register, and Admin Login. Some modules such as Product, Resource Centre, and Services have various sub-modules including Search, Types, Booklet, Videos, Refiling, and Maintenance.

This Website is divided into two parts-

- Front-end
- Back-end

We made use of HTML, CSS, JavaScript, Bootstrap, PHP, and Xampp Server.

A. Front-end

For the front end, we made use of HTML, CSS, JavaScript, and Bootstrap. HTML is used to develop a basic structure of the website. While CSS is used for the designing purpose of this project. We gave the logic by making use of JavaScript and Bootstrap to make the website responsive to add product carts, etc.

B. Back-end

For the back-end purpose, we made use of PHP and the data was getting stored on the local server which is Xampp. So, there was interaction between the back-end and front-end via PHP and JavaScript.

VI. IMPLEMENTATION

A. Module: HOME

Image 2: Module: HOME

The Home Module consists of the Company Name written in the center of the page in large font size. There is also written a brief description of what the company does.

The Home tab is the tab that is shown first when we search for the website. It consists of a background picture suitable for the company's work.

B. Module: ABOUT US

Image 3: Module: ABOUT US

The About Us Module consists of the Vision and Mission of the Company and the Information about the Company, the founder, the products which the company sells, and much more.

There is a wide variety when it comes to buying fire safety equipment according to our needs.

C. Module: PRODUCTS

The module products open up a vast variety of products to buy Including, Fire Alarm, Fire Hydrant, Fire Extinguisher, and much more...

Users can select the product according to their needs and fill in the product detailson the contact us page. So, the data of the user is directly stored in the database.

Image 4: Module: PRODUCTS, Alarm

The above image shows the image of a Fire Hydrant along with a detailed description of the product and a button that says, Know more... So, after clicking the know more

button one can get more detailed information about the product.

Image 5: Module: PRODUCTS, Hydrant

Image 6: Module: PRODUCTS, Hydrant

Similarly in the above two Images, the first Image consists of a Fire Hydrant along with its brief description and a know more button. When a user clicks on the Know

More button it redirects to the second image shown above which consists of three different types of hydrants. Here, the user can go and buy the desired product.

Image 7: Module: PRODUCTS, Fire Extinguisher

Similarly goes for Fire Extinguisher and other products...

to know how to make use of the products, it consists of direct YouTube videos which help a user to know how to use them. It also consists of a booklet that includes various types of products in it.

D. Module: RESOURCE CENTER

The resource center consists of two modules which are booklets and videos. The resource center modules help users

Image 8: Module: RESOURCE CENTER

The above Image shows the Types of fire safety devices that are present in the market.

Image 9: Module: RESOURCE CENTER

The above Image shows a video link consisting of information about how to operate Fire safety devices.

Image 10: Module: RESOURCE CENTER

The above Image shows a video link containing information about using Fire safety devices.

E. Module: SERVICES

Services modules give us detailed Information about the types of services that the Industrial Trading Corporation Company gives. It gives various services such as Refilling, and Maintenance.

Image 11: Module: SERVICES

The above Image gives detailed Information about the services and it also consists of an Image of a Fire Extinguisher into it.

Image 12: Module: SERVICES, Maintenance

The above Image is a type of service – Maintenance. It consists of an Image where a person is doing maintenance of a Fire Extinguisher and detailed Information about the types of maintenance this company does.

The above Image is a type of service – Refiling. It consists of an Image where a person is doing refiling of a Fire Extinguisher and detailed Information about the types of refiling this company does.

F. Module: CONTACT US

The contact us module is responsible for direct contact with the company – Industrial Trading Corporation.

Image 13: Module: CONTACT US

Image 14: Module: CONTACT US)

G. Module: Login Page

Admin can log in via the login page and can access the data of the customers.

Image 15: Module: LOGIN PAGE)

H. Module: Registration Page

If the admin is not registered, he/she can register themselves and then go for login.

Image 16: Module: REGISTRATION PAGE

I. Module: Database

The data is directly stored in the database when the user enters its information on the website.

Image 17: Module: DATABASE)

VII. REQUIREMENTS

A. Hardware Requirements

- Hard disk
- Pen drive
- Laptop/ Computer

B. Software Requirements

- Dreamweaver Application
- Notepad++
- xampp-win32-1.7.4-VC6-installer
- XAMPP Control Pane
- CorelDRAW X7 (64-Bit)
- Go Daddy-Domain Server.

VIII. ADVANTAGES

A. Time Efficiency

It saves a lot of time for the users who need new fire safety equipment as they don't have to move from one shop to another. Users can also compare different websites.

B. Flexible GUI

Flexible GUI means the website is completely responsive and easy to understand the graphics.

C. Easy to Use and Update

Management of the website is quite easier. It is also helpful in managing the records of clients in the database.

D. Financial Benefits

This website will Increase the public reach which means good advertisement so no need to spend more money on advertisement.

E. Promote and Sell Products & Services

Provides Photos and detailed descriptions of Products or Services.

F. Two-Way Communication

There is direct communication between the customer and the company so the communication between them is much faster and smoother.

G. Improve Customer Service

As the data is directly saved into the database so the employees of the company can directly contact the customers.

H. Increase Customers

E-commerce websites are trending so this will help to reach customers around the globe.

I. Opportunity

This website helps us to gain profits in the business.

J. Better Relationship

Having an E-commerce website will help to make a better relationship between the customer and the Company.

IX. APPLICATION*A. Digital Maintenance of Records*

The database is only accessed by the admin. The data is saved directly into the database. So, the management of the data becomes easier. The accessibility of the data becomes easier. So, the maintenance of the data becomes easy.

B. Digital generation of records

As the data filled in by the customer is saved into the database directly. So, the records are auto generated.

C. Manufacturing

An E-commerce website also sells Manufactured products. Also, this website consists of the manufacturing part.

D. Marketing

An E-commerce website helps with marketing the products and services of the company. It helps to gain customers throughout the globe.

Image 18: Marketing

E. Auctions

An E-commerce website helps in selling goods and services online to customers. It includes auctions (electronic auctions) which help in bidding. Bidding is a type of auction that helps multiple types of buyers to bid for a product.

F. E-Commerce Applications

E-commerce websites are helpful in marketing, productivity, profit in business, and much more... One can buy products from the E-commerce website through a single product, wholesale, or retail method.

G. Online stock trading

Many websites offer many different kinds of information related to business and provide several graphs for the analysis purpose for the evaluation and the conclusion from the analysis of the graphs.

X. FUTURE SCOPE

For now, the project is very limited. We have implemented only a few things into this E-commerce Website. The Website includes direct communication between the user and the company, one can see a wide range of Products on this website. One can witness a lot of resources present on the website.

In the Future, we are planning to add a direct payment option so that a user can directly place their orders without communication with the company. In the Future, we are planning to add more features to the website and to include more products and services from the company side. We are planning to make this website dynamic in the future so that we can make the changes to the website easily.

XI. CONCLUSION

As we know, E-commerce websites are really helpful in making our business grow. An E-commerce website has many advantages such as Time Efficiency, Flexible GUI, Ease to use and Update, Financial Benefits, Promote, and Sell Products & Services, Two-Way Communication, Improve Customer Service, Increase Customers, Opportunity, Better Relationships, and much more... It has many applications too such as Digital Maintenance of

Records, Digital generation of records, Manufacturing, Marketing, Auctions, E-Commerce Applications, Online stock trading, and much more... So, An E-commerce website is beneficial for maintaining records, direct communication between the user and the company and it has a lot of plus points. In the coming Era, E-commerce websites are going to boom in the industry. We can conclude that an E-commerce website is a must to grow the business faster.

LETTER FROM THE COMPANY / APPROVAL CERTIFICATE

INDUSTRIAL TRADING CORPORATION

- * Sales & Service of Firefighting Equipments
- * ABC, Stored Pressure Refilling Expert
- * Co2 Gas Catradge Refilling
- * All Types of Fire Extinguisher Supplied with spares
- * Fixing of Fire Hydrant System, Sprinklers System Fitting

Office : Indora, Jaripatka Road, Behind Bara Kholi, Republican Nagar, Mate Chowk, Nagpur-440014.
 email: industrialtradingcorp2012@gmail.com Mob.: 9850616532, 7038702335

Ref. No.: _____ Date: 19/02/22

To,
 The Principal,
 NIT Polytechnic ,Nagpur

Subject: Application for Granting permission to develop website for our company

Respected Sir/Mam,

Students of Final year of your college NIT Polytechnic Nagpur came for a survey at our site and they are willing to develop a website for our shop . So, we are giving permission to develop a website to the following students.

Group Members:

- 1) Shruti L. Shahare
- 2) Vishakha S. Shende
- 3) Payal H. Zodape
- 4) Alisha L. Meshram
- 5) Yogesh A. Rahangdale

Thanking you!

For Industrial Trading Corporation

Proprietor

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